

Minimal Information versus Stochasticity in an Ideal Gas

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Classical statistical mechanics of an ideal gas is usually described as applying to a system consisting of a very large number of particles (10^{23}) for which one cannot practically track all trajectories. Furthermore, such a system is said to be described by single parameters such as volume V , pressure P , and temperature T . In the case of an ideal gas, one has $PV=nRT$, so that $dE = -PdV$ (no heat flow) means that $-PdV = nRT d \ln(1/V)$. Here $1/V$ is a probability, and $\ln(1/V)$ information in information theory. These notions seem to be directly related to the statistical gas, but we argue that they appear for a deterministic system of a few particles.

We consider first the case of a deterministic single particle in a one dimensional box and then a small number of deterministic single particles to see how a constant P is directly linked to uniform distribution in the volume, even for a deterministic system. The uniform distribution suggests a minimal amount of information as well as a constant P (averaged over a small time) and so the stochasticity seems to be related to finding a particular single particle at any given point x . If one thinks in terms of identical particles, then a uniform distribution in x does not seem to be linked to stochasticity. Thus, the stochasticity seems to be related to the Newtonian idea of identifying each particle.

Given that $d \ln(1/V)$ appears for a small number of deterministic particles, it seems to be linked to the fact that one wishes to have the deterministic system describe a constant P instead of $P(t)$ which means that one has minimized information. This, in turn, is associated with a uniform distribution in space (again minimal information), but there does not seem to be stochasticity in the deterministic example using a few particles.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

Classical statistical mechanics, as applied to an ideal gas, is sometimes described as statistical because one cannot practically follow each trajectory because there are so many (10^{23}). Furthermore, like thermodynamics, single values such as pressure P , volume V and temperature T are said to characterize such a gas in equilibrium. One has the following equations:

$$PV = nRT \quad ((1a)) \quad E = \frac{3}{2} nRT \quad (\text{three dimensions-only translational motion}) \quad ((1b))$$

$$dE = \text{delta heat} + \text{delta Work} \quad \text{where delta Work} \rightarrow -P dV \quad ((1c))$$

$$\text{As a result of } ((1a)) \text{ (the ideal gas law) one has: Work} = -nRT dV/V \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{For an ideal gas with no change in heat: } dE(T) = nRT dV/V \quad ((3))$$

Scaling volume means that dV/V cancels these factors as they are not present in $dE(T)$.

$-dV/V = d \ln(1/V)$ where $1/V$ is a uniform probability and $\ln(1/V)$ information in information theory. We ask, however, whether such ideas are already present for one or a few deterministic particles.

One Deterministic Particle

Consider a single deterministic particle whose trajectory is:

$x = vt + B$ ((4)) in a one-dimensional box, where B is known and v is constant

In such a case, the particle hits the wall of the box and reflects elastically. If one wishes to impart energy to the particle, one may move the wall in (decrease volume) at precisely the time at which the particle hits the wall. This is a Newtonian reaction which does not require any sense of statistical mechanics, namely:

$F(x) dx = d .5mv^2$ ((5)) where x =the edge of the box at the time the particle is there

One may ask: Is there any relevance to the constraint of the length of the box? In ((5)) there is no mention of the length. It seems that the box length is only relevant if one considers the sense of work/time (i.e. an average work). If the particle is not present at the edge of the box, then no work is done changing V . Thus. If one has two boxes of lengths L and $L/2$, t is half for the second and work/time before the first hit is:

W for the first box and $2W$ for the second.

This suggests that work/time is proportional to $1/L$.

This result follows by introducing time considerations linked to the length (volume) constraint and emerges for a completely deterministic particle and yet is identical to dV/V from PdV using $PV=nRT$. Furthermore, dV/V was argued to represent $- d \ln(1/V)$, where $1/V$ is a probability and $\ln(1/V)$ information in information theory. One may ask:Where is the probability or information for a single deterministic particle? We note that dL/L only appears if one divides by the time of a cycle. In other words, one finds the work done per cycle and the cycle differs based on length. We try to carry this idea over to a small number of particles which are again deterministic.

Small Number of Deterministic, Constant Speed Particles

The idea of thermodynamics and statistical mechanics is to have a constant P against a wall. The problem is that this only seems to hold if one averages over a small time because at any instant, one does not necessarily have the same number of particles or same momenta striking the wall. If $N \rightarrow$ infinite, then P is constant, but for smaller numbers, even large, this is an approximation, albeit a very good one it seems. The term $-PdV$ appears to apply to the work delivered in a small period of time. If one has a box with a small number of deterministic, constant speed particles and one wishes to do work $-PdV$, one should be able to choose any time with constant probability for this work. This means that a small time interval associated with

each time chosen should yield a hit with the same number of particles. Given that the number is small, one may suggest one hit. This means, in turn, that the completely deterministic particles must be uniformly distributed over the box length L (one dimension). One may have each particle slightly above the other in the y direction (motion in x), so that when they change direction they don't collide with each other.

A uniform distribution, even for completely deterministic particles suggests a lack of information, i.e. bias information which would favour any x in L . Thus, there is minimal information, but no real sense of stochasticity. If one knows the time at which the wall is moved dV , then one knows precisely which particle strikes and receives energy. One still has:

$$dE(T) = -PdV \text{ where } P \text{ is proportional to } 1/V \text{ (here } 1/L \text{ in one dimension) ((6))}$$

A uniform distribution is usually associated with probability, but we argue that it may equally well apply to deterministic particles. It is necessary to create the notion of a single P value against the wall and the choice of any time for moving the wall an amount dV . In an ideal gas, one may argue that if particles are labeled, one would not know at which x point to find particle i , with equal probability for each dx . In such a case, there is stochasticity if one considers each particle as being labeled. We argue, however, that for a deterministic system with labeled particles, a uniform distribution in x does not seem to be linked with any kind of stochasticity and gives rise to the same dV/V of an ideal gas.

Conclusion

In conclusion, an ideal gas is said to contain so many particles that one cannot track all trajectories and that in the absence of a potential $V(x)$, there is equal probability for a single particle to be at any. Furthermore, the ideal gas law, $PV=nRT$, leads to $dW = -PdV = -nRT dV/V = nRT d(\ln(1/V))$. $1/V$ is a probability from a uniform distribution and $\ln(1/V)$ information, in information theory.

We argue here that these information theoretical results seem to already be present in a deterministic treatment in one dimension. We suggest that if one considers a small number of equally spaced deterministic, constant v , particles along the length L of a 1-D box, then one receives equally spaced strikes with the wall suggesting a constant pressure in each Δt between hits. Furthermore, if one decides to do work by changing V (i.e. dV), then one imparts energy to one particle. (The particles move one above the other.) As a result, one has a uniform distribution in L (or V) even for deterministic particles and this suggests a probability of $1/V$ even though there is no particular probability in the deterministic case. The $1/V$ probability applies because for a different L , the spacing is different and directly linked to L . This means that one considers work done in a tiny time interval, namely that of the time between particles. This then leads to dV/V which appears to be statistical, but is rather linked to a uniform distribution which is required, even in the case of determinism, to create equal pressure in time. If one does not have equal pressure in time, then one cannot characterize the deterministic system by a constant P , but rather requires $P(t)$. Thus, minimal information for P , i.e. $P=\text{constant}$, implies a uniform distribution in x , which also represents minimal information in space.